

Psychological Empowerment and its Relationship to Emotional Tact among Female Students at the College of Basic Education

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Abstract: The research aimed to identify psychological empowerment among female students at the College of Basic Education and to identify emotional tact among female students at the College of Basic Education. It also aimed to identify the nature of the relationship between psychological empowerment and emotional tact. The current research sample was limited to (300) female students from the College of Basic Education for the academic year 2023-2024 from the scientific and humanities departments. The researchers built two scales, one to measure psychological empowerment and the other to measure emotional tact. The psychological empowerment scale in its final form consists of 30 paragraphs, while the emotional tact scale consists of 30 paragraphs after deleting two paragraphs. The psychometric properties of the items were extracted for validity, reliability, and discrimination. After using the appropriate statistical means and according to the objectives, the results showed that there are statistically significant differences in emotional tact and psychological empowerment in favor of the research sample of female students from the College of Basic Education. The results also showed a significant correlation between psychological empowerment and emotional tact.

Key points: Psychological empowerment, emotional tact, female students at the College of Basic Education.

First Chapter

Definition of the research

Research Problem:

There is no doubt that emotions have a significant effect on the learning process, which is related to the student's personality, as he is the axis around which the educational process revolves, and which seeks through its educational means to build its personality according to scientific and healthy basis. The educational goal no longer means providing the student with an amount of information, but rather caring for his personality as a whole in its mental and psychological aspects in order to make him a person confident in his abilities and capabilities and aware of his abilities and what he should and must do in terms of effective and purposeful work, through his free choices, which will have consequences, and he must accept those results as a result of his personal doings. Also, he must realize his personal responsibility and work to find links that connect him with others by building social relationships based on love and mutual interaction that allow him to highlight his privacy, uniqueness and distinguish. This requires him to have a personality characterized by emotional tact. (Al-Masoudi, 2002: 6). The segment of young women, especially female university students, is considered one of the most important, most aware and educated segments of society, and caring for them is considered one of the concerns of society as a whole. They are the means of change, construction and progress, or they are the energy on which any development or progress in the country is based, and they must be cared for, given attention and directed. This care must include all

aspects of their personalities (mental, psychological, social and physical). (Al-Shammari, 2001: 2). Emotional tact is also one of the positive aspects of life and represents the ability to face many difficulties and life pressures with acceptance and satisfaction in terms of issuing judgments on them, openness and deep insight in reaching solutions for them instead of removing and narrowing them and facing intensity with courage.

Emotional tact helps people identify how their feelings influence on their thoughts, actions, and behaviors in a way that does not invalidate or deny these emotions, but rather treats them as a source of data through which these thoughts and feelings can be managed, and it also becomes possible to learn from them without being dominated by them. Emotional tact consists of four axes: realizing our feelings, knowing these feelings by their names, accepting these feelings, and communicating with the value system. (Abu Halawa, 2021: 65).

In patriarchal societies, there is a disproportionate representation of women in various fields such as politics, law, media and the workforce. In addition, they are more exposed to violence and discrimination. Promising approaches to promoting psychological empowerment in women include transformative group dynamics and empowerment-based interventions. The rationale for such an approach is that psychological empowerment plays a pivotal role in the advancement of women. Not only does it lead to many positive results, such as increased levels of self-esteem, self-efficacy and confidence, an increased sense of control over someone's life, and greater participation in decision-making, but it also helps break down gender stereotypes. These interventions provide a safe and supportive space for women to share Their experiences, strengthening relationships, developing their skills and confidence, and thus motivating them to assume leadership roles. Empowerment is a process of awareness and conscience to build capabilities, which leads to achieving more effective participation and authority in decision-making and control. Empowerment is a process of awareness and conscience to build capacity that leads to greater participation and effective decision-making and control. This involves the ability to get what one wants and influence others about one's interests (Al-Krenawi, A., & Aqrawi, 2017:301).

Psychological empowerment is characterized by the individual's belief in his ability to impose control over his own life and make a positive change in the world. Specifically, women who experience high levels of psychological empowerment show a greater tendency to participate in collective actions, which serves to advance efforts toward gender equality more broadly. Psychological empowerment is a combination of self-esteem, self-efficacy, self-determination, self-confidence, self-awareness, and positive thinking that ultimately leads to women's well-being and happiness. The problem of the current research can be summarized in answering the following question: What is the extent of psychological empowerment and emotional tact among female students at the College of Basic Education?

The Importance of Research:

Caring for university students means caring for society as a whole, as they are the segment that bears the responsibility of leading that society in the future. Therefore, they must be cared for by developing their creative and productive energies and preventing them from turning into destructive energies that lead to the destruction of themselves and society at the same time. (Al-Ahmadi, 2007: 86).

The youth stage is characterized by emotional tension because of the problems of this stage, including the young man's attempt to choose a profession that suits his abilities and ambitions, and economic independence. They are at the beginning of the long struggle to achieve a respectful life in the future (Salman, 1990: 419). That is, attention must be paid to the emotional or affective side of the individual, considering that it is one of the means of the individual's adaptation to the successive and conflicting variables that surround him, based on the fact that the individual's feelings and emotions are among the most important influences in directing his behavior in general, his way of thinking, issuing judgments, and making decisions in general.

This depends on the fact that accurate and rapid perception of emotions allows for quick and accurate emotional and behavioral responses. This is because without this skill, these responses tend to be delayed later and thus are inappropriate for the situation, or in other words, the individual loses his sensitivity to the behavioral situation and becomes inappropriate in his ability to face challenges appropriately. (Salman, 1990: 419).

Since the emotional aspect is important because it represents an aspect of psychological development and affects the direction of the child's behavior, studying this aspect and its components affects the behavior and actions of children in their future lives, which has negative or positive effects on society. Emotional tact is one of the most important aspects of emotional development (Ministry of Education, 1985: 5).

Therefore, the importance of the current study derives from the importance of emotional tact in the individual's life and its impact on emotional growth and personality building in his future life. Emotional tact, as described by Sylvester (1995), is an effective means of communication beyond the limits of written or spoken words. Emotions often form mental tendencies or unconscious tendencies (Shuaib, 2022: 49).

Emotional tact refers to dealing consciously and productively with our internal emotional experiences. Emotional tact is accepting all our feelings, even negative ones, and treating our emotions as a source of our personal data. We also focused on the type of words we use to describe our feelings, which we tend to choose easily and quickly even though we do not realize the exact reason for this. The essence behind our feelings and emotions, and we are not skilled or effective in reading our emotional data. (Capriz, 2020) talks about emotional tact, describing it as the sixth sense, and we are facing a special psychological state with the emergence the virus of Covid-19, characterized by fear, anxiety, feelings of isolation, feelings of anger, sadness and disappointment, although these feelings and sensations are collective and not individual. It seems logical, but it does not make us enjoy reassurance in it. (Shuaib, 2022: 49).

She also remembers that we speak about 16,000 words and wonders: How many words have we not spoken and are stored in our minds? She also comments, saying that most of these words that we utter are not facts, but rather judgments around which our emotions revolve, some of which are positive and others negative, and this does not conflict with the nature of the human soul, and these are our minds that perform the function for which they were designed, which is trying to anticipate problems and solve them to avoid them. Possible negative consequences. This can happen in one of two ways: dealing with ideas as if they were facts or avoiding them. The concept of emotional tact is that an individual should be flexible in his thoughts and feelings to have good reactions to daily life situations. On the other hand, emotional hardness represents an individual's tendency to become attached to thoughts, feelings, and behaviors that do not provide flexible solutions to life's problems and pressures. He also proposes a pattern of emotional tact in four stages: exploring the emotion, releasing the emotion, defeat the causes of the emotion, and moving on. By exploration, we mean that the individual faces his emotions with curiosity and at the same time with acceptance, because negatives are normal and natural things. "Negative thoughts and feelings" are an unavoidable part of the human experience, and we cannot expect to simply stop negative feelings such as fear, anger, insecurity, and sadness and replace them with feelings of confidence and happiness, but what happens is that the efforts made tend to be suppressed or leaked in an unfamiliar or unexpected way. It becomes more intense than it was before because of its aggravation in the subconscious mind. Therefore, negative feelings for some reason may be one of the vital signs that help the individual recognize them and move on to the basic problems and challenges in our lives. Instead of trying to escape from our problems, it is recommended to face them with an open heart and in an acceptable way. Therefore, this step is considered the first step on the path to emotional tact, which represents confronting negative feelings instead of trying to suppress them or minimize them. Perhaps this step requires a degree of courage, self-acceptance, self-compassion, and pressing feelings under the logo "You are here, and I am here: let's talk" (Abdul Hamid, 2021: 8).

She discussed the concept of emotional tact through a survey of about 70,000 people and concluded that 66% of them judge themselves because of what are called negative feelings such as sadness and anger, while the last third had neutralized these feelings as a result of being positive, which was the reason behind correcting their value judgments. She even called for the logo "Be positive" and considered it the heart and essence of everything in our lives because negative feelings are the basis of all our psychological disorders. She also focused on her interpretation of our behaviors on our responses to the state of disorder, as it is like a volcano that, if it explodes, destroys everything. This is what we call as psychologists' exaggeration, which the more we try to ignore it, the more its grip on us increases. You may think that you are in control, but it is a kind of temporary deception until the explosion occurs. Also remember that you are not your feelings and emotions, you own the emotions, and they do not own you (Shuaib, 2022: 51). A psychologically empowered woman has the ability to improve her self-image and overcome shame. Empowering women means enabling them to access skills, knowledge, and adapt with stress and shocks in the present as well as the future.

Using the four knowledges of Thomas and Felthous's (1990) model, Spreitzer developed and experimentally validated a multidimensional measure of psychological empowerment in the workplace. He defines empowerment as a core motivation that is manifested in four knowledges that reflect the individual's orientation toward his or her role at work. The four cognitions are meaning, competence, self-determination, and influence. Meaning refers to a sense of purpose or personal connection to work. Empowered people feel that their work is important to them and that they care about what they do. Competence reflects individuals' beliefs that they have the skills and abilities to do their job well. Self-determination refers to a sense of freedom and how individuals do their work. Influence describes the belief that individuals can influence the system in which they live.

From all of this, we can summarize the importance of the research and the need for it as follows:

1. The importance of emotional tact and psychological empowerment because they are closely related to self-efficacy and the ability to make decisions regarding the future and the ability to deal with others and coexist with them according to what the situations require.
2. The university stage is one of the important stages in the lives of female students and working with the female student segment at this stage has its characteristics and advantages and needs to be studied.
3. The researchers hope that the study will open the way for other studies that address emotional tact or psychological empowerment in other samples.

Research objectives: -

The current research aimed to: -

1. Identify psychological empowerment among female students at the College of Basic Education
2. Identify emotional tact among female students at the College of Basic Education.
3. Identify the nature of the relationship between psychological empowerment and emotional tact.

The Research limits: -

The current research is limited to female students from the College of Basic Education/ Mustansiriyah University for the academic year 2023-2024 and from both specializations (scientific - humanities).

The Definition of terms: -

The researcher defined the following terms: -

Firstly: - Psychological empowerment

(Bandura, 1969) defines it as "the process of reinforce the sense of self-efficacy, which is a source of strength and energy that helps the individual to free himself from the restrictions imposed by others and can achieve the goals he seeks and coexist with the requirements of the situation. Individuals who feel psychologically empowered can work more effectively and deal with the people around them" (Bandura, 1969: 191-215).

Short & Rinehart's, 1992 define it as "the individual's beliefs and sense of independence in performing daily work tasks, the ability to bear professional responsibility, the feeling of importance and self-efficacy and influence on benefiting, and their capacity to make proper decisions." (Jamian & Abdallah & Fook, 2019: 4).

(Spreitzer, 1995) defines it as "the individual's awareness that his work has meaning and value, that he has the competence and ability to accomplish tasks, and that he has faith in himself and his ability to choose and organize the task that he must accomplish." (1442: 1995 Spreitzer).

(Brancato, 2000) defines it as "the individual's beliefs about his ability to perform a task well, and it is a means of encouraging the individual to make decisions, enriching his experience and sense of self-determination, and self-governance in influencing results, and that he is less afraid and has the ability to control and control his external environment, and makes them more creative by trying what is new" (Abdel Fattah, 2017: 411)

The researchers adopted the definition of (Bandura, 1969) because it is the basis on which the scale was prepared. As for the operational definition, it is: "The degree that the respondent obtains on the psychological empowerment scale prepared in the current research."

Secondly: Emotional Tact

Maghribi (2008)

"The ability to pay attention and understand personal emotions and feelings well and understand and formulate them clearly and organize them according to the observation and accurate perception of the emotions and feelings of others, to reach positive emotional and social relationships with them that help the individual to develop mentally, emotionally and professionally, and learn more positive life skills" (Maghribi, 2008: 23).

David, 2016 defines it as "a creative approach that simulates the stresses of life, through which thinking, reason, and values are controlled instead of possessing and controlling emotions and feelings in expressing our reactions. It represents the ability to recognize the inner world of our thoughts, feelings, and emotions and accept them with curiosity without judging them." (Shuaib, 2022: 80).

Abdul Hamid (2021) defines it as "the individual's ability to pay attention and be well aware of his emotions and feelings, understand and formulate them, monitor the accurate awareness of the emotions and feelings of others, and clearly integrate with them and organize them according to positive emotional and social reactions. Relationships that help the individual achieve intellectual, psychological and professional progress and learn more positive life skills." (Abdul Hamid, 2021: 8).

The two researchers adopted the definition of David, 2016 because it is the basis on which the scale was prepared.

As for the procedural definition, it is: "the score that the respondent gains on the emotional tactility scale used in the current research."

Secondly Chapter

Theoretical Framework and Previous Studies

Theories that Explained Psychological Empowerment:

Kanungo & Conger Pa/

Kanungo & Conger (1988) defined empowerment as a psychological concept of self-efficacy, and adopted the individual psychological concept of empowerment, as they defined empowerment as a process of enhancing the sense of self-efficacy of working individuals by identifying the conditions that enhance the sense of weakness and getting rid of them through formal and informal organizational practices that rely on providing information about self-efficacy. They also mentioned that empowerment is synonymous with the concept of power, as it can be viewed from two angles. The first: empowerment can be viewed as a communication complex, as empowerment implicitly indicates the delegation of authority. The second: empowerment can be viewed as a psychological complex, as empowerment indicates more than a partnership in authority. In contrast to the delegation of authority, empowerment includes a factor of motivation and motivation through empowering the person and activating his/her own ability. Therefore, empowerment gives the person the ability and not a delegation. (Abu Al-Hassan, 2021: 1305).

Zimmerman's theory

Zimmerman (1995) described psychological empowerment in his theory as a dynamic state and not a fixed personality trait, which explains that every individual can become empowered over time in the presence of an empowering process and an empowering environment, and psychological empowerment varies across different areas of life: family, school, and work, especially with children and youth. Zimmerman added that individuals' families initially lack confidence in psychological empowerment programs, and this confidence increases over time. The psychological empowerment process is an interactive process that leads to a certain psychological state, and this state changes over time and across the context in which it occurs. This means that an individual may feel empowered at work but feel helpless and disempowered while interacting with the school system, especially children and women. Therefore, empowerment programs and measures vary according to the area of helplessness and difficulty.

Zimmerman was interested in presenting three dimensions of empowerment theory, which are values, information, processes, and results. **First**, empowerment values provide values. Empowering values are a system of beliefs or a belief system that guides how specialists and clients work together. This value includes concern for issues of health, adaptation, efficiency, and medical health systems. The empowerment approach considers normality versus illness, efficiency and worthiness versus disability and deficiency. **Second**, empowerment processes refer to the mechanisms and means through which individuals, organizations, and societies gain control, or mastery over aspects that concern them. They also develop intelligent criticism of their environments and participate in making decisions that affect their lives. Empowerment processes provide individuals with opportunities that include developing and practicing the necessary skills and helping the individual on how to provide an intelligent critical analysis of their environment. Third, empowerment outcomes are represented in the effects and new situations resulting from the application of empowerment programs, as shown through measurement processes, and they mean the dependent variables on the basis that Operations and efforts are stable variables (Al-Nimr, 2020: 1365)

Zimmerman believes that individuals feel higher levels of psychological empowerment to the extent that they actually integrate into performing the roles assigned to them, and that psychological empowerment includes the growth of participatory competence based on a positive self-concept and a positive sense of competence on the one hand, and on an analytical understanding of the social and political environment, and on developing personal and social resources for positive social work on the other hand

Empowered individuals view themselves more positively in their work and are evaluated by colleagues as more competent in accomplishing their work, and psychological empowerment includes individuals' belief in the meaning of the work they perform, their ability to perform it better, their sense of self-efficacy and independence, in addition to their impact on the outputs or results of work (Menon, 2001: 153).

Social Cognitive Theory

Social cognition theory, formulated by Albert Bandura in the 1960s, emphasizes the importance of observational learning and social modeling in the development of behavior. It assumes that individuals acquire knowledge by observing others and receiving rewards or punishments for their actions. This theory is relevant to explaining how individuals become empowered because they can acquire knowledge by observing others who are empowered and by being rewarded for their empowering actions. When individuals witness others rewarding their behavior, they are more likely to imitate those actions, which is known as observational learning.

Social cognition theory also emphasizes the priority of self-confidence, which is the belief that one can perform a task competently (Bandura, 1969: 191-215).

Theories that explain emotional tact:

David's theory, 2016

This theory sees that our meeting with our emotions and thoughts, whether positive or negative, is one of the main steps to help us be more emotionally tactful. Negative emotions are a crime that we should be exposed to or ashamed of rather, they are a system like any system that works in the body, the visual system, and the respiratory system. They all provide us with a continuous flow of information that helps us direct our behaviors, regulate our performance, and increase our efficiency. (David S., 2016) identifies four guiding steps to achieve emotional tact:

- When you are exposed to stressful emotional situations such as anger and sadness, do not rush to express them, nor do you bury them inside you or make them appear in front of others. You must learn and understand what emotions are telling you in this stressful situation
- Replace the phrase "I am sad, or I am angry" with "I feel sad, or I feel angry", as this will give you a basic skill in expressing your emotions in front of Yourself, your family, and your colleagues during the emotional state.
- Allow yourself to feel the truth of your emotions and allow others to feel the truth of their emotions.
- Listen to what your emotions want to tell you and always compare it to your values and ethics. (Shuaib, 2022: 76)
- It is important for any individual to know and understand the way of expressing his emotions, but the most important thing is to understand them and interpret his response to emotions. Intelligence has become very important as it has become part of educational programs in schools and universities. The role of these programs is not limited to improving the quality of life for individuals only but has extended to help learners achieve success in what they learn. Positive aspects of emotional intelligence such as: improving decision-making, improving communication with oneself and others, and strengthening resilience in the face of crises and adversity. (Shuaib, 2022: 76). **The researcher has adopted this theory.**

(Cox's theory, 2018):

The theory indicated that to achieve emotional tact requires: showing new feelings and thoughts, especially negative ones, with curiosity and accepting them instead of trying to fix them or escape from them, getting out of your internal dialogues to see them as they really are, as they are just feelings that you deal with, getting rid of negative thoughts and feelings according to your values and principles, continuing to develop and innovate "helpful" habits that keep you motivated in line with your set of personal values, which qualifies you to rebuild the life you want to live and not add

to "things you should do". It also comments that while practicing emotional tact, we find that practicing mindfulness is useful in reducing judgment and that we need to believe everything we believe to create distance and thought. And you see (Shuurman, 2016)

Emotional tact requires the establishment of what is called self-babble or an internal dialogue box between the conscious self on the one hand, and an endless stream of thoughts and feelings that operate without anything hindering their emergence. (Shuaib, 2022: 78).

Lunk's point of view (2002)

Lunk (2002) believes that emotional tact is nothing but a feature that helps the individual to perform his psychological, cognitive and emotional functions in a systematic and integrated method. Emotional tact helps the individual to overcome unbridled instincts, deviations and psychological and mental disorders, as it allows the individual to modify negative feelings and emotions in a manner that suits the requirements of the current moment. This helps the individual to be more positive, as emotional tact regulates the work between the mind and emotions, and thus the individual becomes able to overcome and confront difficulties and has sufficient behavioral flexibility to overcome difficulties. Lunk also believes that the emotionally innovative person can make attempts to control his behavior and change and develop his life. Lunk believes that the emotionally tactful person does not suffer from psychological disorders and diseases because he has a true perception of his feelings and emotions and enjoys credibility in expressing them. Lunk explained that emotional tact is a result of the interaction between the environment and the internal components of the individual. He pointed out that the observing and following-up of the parents for the individual's growth and giving him the opportunity to express his feelings and emotions in a correct and honest manner without resorting to suppressing them makes the life changes that the individual goes through normal (Long, 2002: 6-18).

Thomas's view (2004)

This view was a modification of Lunk's view (2002), and Thomas (2004) modified Lunk's view after conducting a series of research related to emotional tact. Thomas (2004) indicated that emotional tact is merely the result of a balance between reason and emotion and is not a personality feature that helps an individual perform his psychological, cognitive, and emotional functions in an organized and integrated manner. Thomas (2004) believes that the more an individual can produce a kind of balance between reason, or in other words, create a kind of balance between higher mental processes, emotions increase the individual's ability to develop and modify his emotions and express them honestly. Thomas (2004) also linked between mental maturity and emotional tact. Maturity is competence, self-control, and the ability to prevent negative feelings. Thomas (2004) indicates that people who are emotionally tactful have some characteristics, including self-understanding, emotional maturity, enjoyment of life, openness to it, and the ability to put aside their instinctive defenses, they also possess emotional intelligence (Thomas, 2004:22-65).

Previous studies:

Studies that dealt with psychological empowerment:

Al-Dhakhriah Study (2023)

This study aimed to determine the relationship between self-compassion, psychological empowerment of mothers, and the adaptive behavior of their children with learning difficulties in Muscat Governorate. The study was conducted on a random sample of (30) mothers, representing (10.2%) of the study community, to apply the study tools to them, totaling (142) mothers of students with learning difficulties. The researcher used (3) scales in this study, namely: the self-compassion scale prepared by Nef (2003) translated by Al-Jundi and Tantawi (2020), the psychological empowerment scale prepared by (Spreitzer, 1995) translated by Al-Nawajha 2016, and the adaptive behavior scale, prepared and standardized by Nasr and Al-Mufti (2016). The study followed the descriptive correlational approach. The study showed a high association between the level of self-compassion, psychological empowerment and adaptive behavior among mothers of students with

learning difficulties in Muscat Governorate, and a statistically significant correlation between the total score of the self-compassion measure and the total score of the psychological empowerment measure. There was also a strong correlation between the self-compassion and psychological empowerment measures of mothers and the adaptive behavior measure of their children with learning difficulties. In other words, the more self-compassion and psychological empowerment mothers, the more adaptive behavior improves in their children with learning difficulties. The results also showed that there are no statistically significant differences in the level of self-compassion and psychological empowerment among mothers of students with learning difficulties in Muscat Governorate in the study sample consisting of (142) mothers of students with learning difficulties attributed to the following variables (student gender, mother's age), and the nature of work in the self-compassion scale; There are statistically significant differences in the psychological empowerment scale attributed to the variable of the mother's nature of work in favor of working mothers; There are no statistically significant differences in the level of adaptive behavior among students with learning difficulties in Muscat Governorate attributed to the variables (student gender, mother's age, nature of mother's work). (Al-Dhakriah, 2023: A-Y).

Al-Najjar's study (2023)

The study aimed to identify the level of psychological empowerment and academic competence among outstanding students at Palestinian universities, as well as to identify the nature of the relationship between psychological empowerment and academic competence in the study sample, and also to identify the statistically significant differences in the variables of gender, academic level, college, and economic level on the variables of psychological empowerment and academic competence, as the research is considered a quantitative research. To achieve the objectives of the study, the descriptive analytical correlational approach was used, where a stratified random probability sample consisting of (200) outstanding male and female students at Palestinian universities were selected, that is, by (9.1%). The researcher used the psychological empowerment and academic competence scales prepared by her. The study reached the following results: The level of psychological empowerment and academic competence was high, and there was a positive correlation with statistical significance between psychological empowerment and academic competence. (Al-Najjar, 2023: 1621).

Studies on emotional tact

The study of Rask et al. (2002) aimed to identify the levels of emotional tact among students and their relationship to values, on a sample of 245 Finnish students, aged between 13 and 15 years. Using measures specific to the emotional package and a list of values, it was found that girls obtained higher scores in emotional tact compared to males. When comparing the age of 13 to the age of 15 years, it was found that older males and females had higher levels of emotional tact. The results derived from the regression analysis indicated that there is a set of values that statistically significantly predict the level of emotional tact among students. These values are personal balance, safe family relationships, and friendship (Abdul Hamid, 2021: 45).

Abdul Hamid's study (2021)

The study aimed to identify the relationship between will and emotional tact. The study was conducted on a sample of university students amounting to (447) students. The results showed that university students have emotional tact, and showed a moderate correlation between will and emotional tact. The study also examined the relationship between will and emotional tact according to the variables of stage and gender (males - females). The results indicated a moderate relationship between will and emotional tact according to the stage variable. There was also no strong relationship between will and emotional tact according to the gender variable (males - females) (Abdul Hamid, 2021: 17).

Shoaib's study (2022)

The study aimed to identify the prevalence of each of emotional tact, psychological resilience, and emotional intelligence in a sample of (322) university students with an average age of (25.12) and a

standard deviation of (7.73). It also aimed to identify the correlation between the three variables. The study aimed to identify the extent to which each of psychological resilience and emotional intelligence contributes as independent variables in predicting emotional tact. It also aimed to identify the effectiveness of a structural model of the causal relationship among the three variables. The study used the Emotional Tact Scale prepared by (David S., 2016), the Resilience Scale for Adults (RSA) prepared by (Friborg, Hjemdal, Martinussen, & Rosenvinge, 2003), and the Emotional Intelligence Scale prepared by (Schutte N., et al., 1998), and all the scales used were translated into Arabic for the current study. The results indicated that university students enjoy emotional tact, psychological resilience, and emotional intelligence, while no statistically significant correlation between emotional tact and both psychological resilience and emotional intelligence appeared. The effectiveness of both psychological resilience and emotional intelligence in predicting emotional tact among university students was not clear, and therefore it was difficult to test a structural model for the causal relationship between the study variables (Shuaib, 2022: 21-101).

Balancing Previous Studies

Objectives The objectives of previous studies were characterized by clarity and precise formulation, and this was reflected in the processing of data, each according to its classification according to the question associated with it. This benefited the two researchers in formulating the objectives of the current study and made it characterized by the same characteristics that characterized the objectives of previous studies. For example, the study of Al-Dhakriya (2023) aimed to identify the relationship between self-compassion and psychological empowerment of mothers and the adaptive behavior of their children with learning difficulties in Muscat Governorate. The study of Al-Najjar (2023) aimed to identify the level of psychological empowerment and academic competence among outstanding students at Palestinian universities. The study of Rask et al. (2002) aimed to identify the levels of emotional tact among students and their relationship to values on a sample of Finnish students, while the study of Abdul Hamid (2021) aimed to identify the relationship between will and emotional tact. The study of Shuaib (2022) aimed to identify the prevalence of each of emotional tact, psychological resilience, and emotional intelligence.

Samples: The number of samples of previous studies varied between (142-447) individuals who fall within the adolescence and youth stages. This variation in the sample sizes of these studies may be due to the variation in their objectives, design, and the nature of the age group they addressed. In the current study, the researcher chose a sample of (300) female students from the College of Basic Education. **Measurement tools:** The tools used in previous studies were numerous and varied. Some researchers prepared a scale to measure emotional tact and psychological empowerment, while others used a ready-made scale. The two researchers constructed a scale for emotional tact and psychological empowerment.

Statistical methods: Previous studies varied in their use of statistical methods, depending on the objectives of those studies. Some studies used the t-test and Pearson's correlation coefficient, while some studies used the t-test for one sample and two independent samples. The researcher relied in the current research on statistical methods that are compatible with the objectives of her research.

Results: The results of the studies varied according to the different objectives of the studies, and although some of them agreed or matched their results, we will learn about what the results of the current research will enhance after applying the scale and analyzing the data.

Chapter Three

Research Procedures

First: Research community: The current research is determined by female students of the College of Basic Education distributed according to the specialization variable (scientific-human) and morning study for the current academic year 2023-2024, and Table (1) shows this

Table (1). Number of female students studying in the College of Basic Education according to the variable of specialization: scientific and humanities

Sequence	Specialization	Scientific Sections	the total
1	Scientific	Mathematics	451
2		Sciences	238
3		Computers	94
4		Art Education	307
5		First Grade Teacher	365
6		Physical Education	312
7		Psychological Counseling	453
8	Specialization	Islamic Education	421
9		Arabic Language	579
10		Family Education	268
11		Geography	504
12		History	509
13		Special Education	170
14		English Language	306
15		Kindergarten	333
	the total		5310

Second: Research sample: The researchers chose the current research sample, which included 300 female students distributed according to the variable of scientific or human specialization, with 150 female students from the scientific specialization and 150 female students from the humanities specialization. Random, and Table (2) shows this.

Table (2). Distribution of the research sample members according to the variable of specialization

Specialization	Section	العدد
Humanities	Arabic Language	75
	History	75
Scientific	Computers	75
	Mathematics	75
the total		300

Third: - Research tools

First: - Paragraph formulation: - Paragraphs were formulated for the psychological empowerment scale and the emotional tact scale, where the psychological empowerment scale included (30) paragraphs, while the emotional tact scale included (32) paragraphs.

Second: - Paragraph validity: - The items of the psychological empowerment scale and the emotional tact scale were presented in their initial form (Appendix No. 1 and 2) to a group of (10) experts specialized in educational and psychological sciences for the purpose of judging the items of the two scales, identifying valid and invalid paragraphs, and making modifications. And the extent of their suitability and the suitability of the answer alternatives to the scale items. An approval rate of 80% or more was adopted for the paragraph so that it would be considered valid and remain in the scale. In light of the experts' opinions, all items were kept, as they obtained an approval rate of more than 80%, with modifications in the formulation of some items of the scale. Thus, the scale in its initial form consisted of (30) paragraphs, which is the psychological empowerment scale, while the emotional tact scale included (32) paragraphs. Third: Statistical analysis of the scale paragraphs: The researchers used two methods to analyze the paragraphs: A- Calculating the discriminating power. In order to verify the discriminating power of the vocabulary, a random sample of (180) female students from the College of Basic Education was selected. This

is not the main application sample. The grades obtained by the female students were arranged in descending order, i.e. from the highest grade to the lowest grade. Then the top and bottom 27% of the grades were selected to represent the two extreme groups. The two groups included (96) female students, so that each group included (48) female students. Then, the researchers used the (t) test for two independent samples and considered the (t) value as an indicator of the discrimination of each paragraph by comparing it to the tabular value. All paragraphs were distinct at the significance level (0.05) and with a degree of freedom (94), as the tabular value reached (1.986) with the exception of two paragraphs from the emotional tact scale, which are Table (3). (4) This was explained in

Table (3). T-values for paragraphs of the psychological empowerment scale using the two extreme samples method

sequence	Lower group 27%		Lower group %27		Calculated T-value	Significance level	sequence	Lower group 27%		Lower group %27		Calculated T-value	Significance level
	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation				Arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation		
1	3.9583	.20194	2.8750	.44363	15.398	mark	16	3.5000	.50529	2.4167	.57735	9.783	mark
2	3.9167	.27931	2.8125	.49060	13.551	mark	17	3.4583	.50353	2.3750	.56962	9.872	mark
3	3.8750	.33422	2.8333	.47639	12.401	mark	18	3.4375	.50133	2.3333	.55862	10.192	mark
4	3.8542	.35667	2.6875	.71923	11.898	mark	19	3.4167	.49822	2.3125	.55183	10.289	mark
5	3.8125	.39444	2.7500	.52592	11.197	mark	20	3.3750	.48925	2.2708	.53553	10.546	mark
6	3.7917	.41041	2.7708	.51528	10.736	mark	21	3.3542	.48332	2.2500	.52592	10.710	mark
7	3.7500	.43759	2.6250	.56962	10.851	mark	22	3.3125	.46842	2.2083	.50353	11.124	mark
8	3.7292	.44909	2.5417	.77070	9.223	mark	23	3.2917	.45934	2.1875	.49060	11.383	mark
9	3.7083	.45934	2.6875	.55183	9.850	mark	24	3.2500	.43759	2.1250	.44363	12.508	mark
10	3.6667	.47639	2.6458	.56454	9.574	mark	25	3.2292	.42474	2.1042	.42474	12.976	mark
11	3.6250	.48925	2.6052	.57388	9.378	mark	26	3.1875	.39444	2.0625	.38072	14.218	mark
12	3.6042	.49420	2.5833	.57735	9.306	mark	27	3.1667	.37662	2.0417	.35480	15.063	mark
13	3.5625	.50133	2.4583	.71335	8.774	mark	28	3.1250	.33422	2.0000	.29173	17.569	mark
14	3.5417	.58346	2.5000	.50353	9.364	mark	29	3.1042	.30871	1.9792	.25177	19.566	mark
15	3.5208	.50485	2.4583	.58194	9.555	mark	30	3.0625	.31999	1.9583	.20194	20.217	mark

Table (4). T-values of the items of the emotional tact scale using the two extreme samples method

no	Lower group 27%		Lower group %27		Calculated T-value	Significance level	no	Lower group 27%		Lower group %27		Calculated T-value	Significance level
	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation				Arithmetic mean	standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	standard deviation		
1	3.8333	.37662	3.6250	.86603	1.528	not mark	17	3.3333	.47639	2.1458	.46078	12.413	mark
2	3.7917	.41041	2.4583	.68287	11.595	mark	18	3.3125	.46842	2.1042	.42474	13.240	mark
3	3.7500	.43759	2.4792	.68384	10.845	mark	19	3.2917	.45934	1.9792	.52550	13.028	mark
4	3.7292	.44909	2.4792	.68384	10.586	mark	20	3.2500	.43759	1.9375	.47964	14.006	mark
5	3.6875	.46842	2.4375	.68125	10.475	mark	21	3.2292	.42474	1.9167	.45351	14.635	mark
6	3.7917	.41041	3.6250	.84110	1.234	not mark	22	3.1875	.39444	1.8750	.39275	16.336	mark
7	3.6250	.48925	2.3333	.66311	10.860	mark	23	3.1667	.37662	1.8750	.39275	16.446	mark
8	3.6042	.49420	2.2917	.77070	9.932	mark	24	3.1250	.33422	1.8542	.35667	18.013	mark
9	3.5833	.49822	2.3958	.67602	9.797	mark	25	3.1042	.30871	1.8542	.35667	18.359	mark
10	3.5417	.50353	2.3542	.66811	9.834	mark	26	3.0625	.24462	1.8542	.35667	19.356	mark
11	3.5000	.50529	2.3125	.65740	9.922	mark	27	3.0417	.20194	1.8542	.35667	20.073	mark
12	3.4792	.50485	2.2917	.65097	9.987	mark	28	2.9792	.14434	1.9167	.27931	23.414	mark
13	3.4375	.50133	2.1667	.72445	9.994	mark	29	2.9583	.20194	1.8750	.33422	19.221	mark
14	3.4167	.49822	2.2083	.61742	10.552	mark	30	2.9167	.27931	1.8333	.37662	16.007	mark
15	3.3958	.49420	2.1667	.59549	11.005	mark	31	2.8542	.41203	1.6458	.48332	13.181	mark
16	3.3750	.48925	2.1250	.56962	11.533	mark	32	2.8525	.44513	1.5833	.49822	12.746	mark

B- The relationship of the paragraph to the total score The discrimination coefficient of the paragraphs of the psychological empowerment and emotional tact scale was extracted using the Pearson correlation equation between the scores of individuals on each paragraph and their total scores on the scale for (180) questionnaires, which are the same questionnaires that were subjected to analysis using the two extreme samples method. It was found that all the correlation coefficients were distinctive when compared to the values of the tabular correlation coefficient, with the exception of two paragraphs of the emotional tact scale, and Table (5) and Table (6) illustrate this.

Table (5). Correlation coefficients between each paragraph of the psychological empowerment scale and its total score

no	Correlation coefficient								
1	0.37	7	0.58	13	0.30	19	0.40	25	0.35
2	0.56	8	0.40	14	0.43	20	0.51	26	0.59

3	0.66	9	0.69	15	0.60	21	0.38	27	0.51
4	0.47	10	0.38	16	0.77	22	0.40	28	0.62
5	0.44	11	0.35	17	0.46	23	0.49	29	0.70
6	0.40	12	0.46	18	0.50	24	0.86	30	0.33

Table (6). Correlation coefficients between each paragraph of the emotional tact scale and the total score on it

no	Correlation coefficient						
1	0.10	9	0.64	17	0.31	25	0.46
2	0.82	10	0.46	18	0.40	26	0.48
3	0.64	11	0.48	19	0.38	27	0.39
4	0.84	12	0.42	20	0.49	28	0.44
5	0.80	13	0.56	21	0.24	29	0.71
6	0.05	14	0.51	22	0.28	30	0.54
7	0.70	15	0.44	23	0.40	31	0.60
8	0.71	16	0.40	24	0.35	32	0.66

Fourth: Correcting the scale: The psychological empowerment scale in its final form consists of (30) paragraphs, each with four alternatives (strongly agree, agree, disagree, strongly disagree). When correcting, the paragraphs are given weights (1, 2, 3), while the emotional tact scale consists of (30) paragraphs, each with four alternatives (strongly agree, agree, disagree, strongly disagree). When correcting, the paragraphs are given weights (1, 2, 3). Fifth: The validity index of the scales. Validity is one of the important characteristics that must be taken into account in constructing psychological scales. A valid scale is one that actually measures what it claims to measure, or its paragraphs are supposed to measure. The best way to extract apparent validity is to present the scale to a group of experts (arbitrators) to judge its suitability in measuring the characteristic to be measured. This type of validity was achieved in the psychological empowerment scale and the emotional tact scale, when the items of the two scales were presented to a group of experts to evaluate them and to judge the validity of the items and alternatives.

Sixth: The stability index of the scales. The stability was extracted by the retest method. To extract the stability in this way, the researchers reapplied the scale to a sample of research individuals, numbering (50) female students. The time period between the first and second application was ten days. Then, the Pearson coefficient was calculated between the individuals' scores in the two applications, and it reached (0.85) for the psychological empowerment scale and (0.80) for the emotional tact scale. It can be said that the current scales enjoy a high degree of stability.

Fourth. Final application: After the researchers completed preparing the psychological empowerment scale and the emotional tact scale (Appendix 4 and 5) in their final form, they were applied to the applied research sample, which amounted to (300) female students, who were selected randomly, distributed according to gender.

Fifth: Statistical methods

To process the data included in the research, the researchers used the following statistical methods:

1. Pearson's correlation coefficient to find the stability of the scale used in the research and the relationship between the variables and the relationship of the paragraph to the total score.
2. T-test for one sample to compare the achieved mean with the theoretical mean of the psychological empowerment and emotional tact scale
3. T-test for two independent samples to reveal the discriminatory power of the research variables

Chapter Four

Research Results

First: Presentation and Discussion of Results

This chapter includes a presentation of the results reached by the current research according to its established objectives, and a discussion of those results in light of the theoretical framework and previous studies in this research, as follows:

1. Identifying psychological empowerment among female students of the College of Basic Education

The arithmetic mean of the research sample on the psychological empowerment scale was (87.1400) and a standard deviation of (9.45861), while the hypothetical mean was (75), and after applying the t-test for one sample, it was found that the calculated t-value was (22.231), which is significant at the level of (0.05) and a degree of freedom of (299), indicating that female students of the College of Basic Education have psychological empowerment, and Table (7) shows this.

Table (7). T-test for the significance of the differences between the average scores of psychological empowerment and the hypothetical mean of the sample

Sample	no	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	hypothetical average	Calculated T value	tabular T value	level of significance (0.05)
Students	300	87.1400	9.45861	75	22.231	1.960	Significant

It is clear from the table above that there are statistically significant differences in favor of the research sample in psychological empowerment, as the arithmetic mean of the sample is higher than its theoretical mean in the scale for the scale. By comparing the calculated T-value with the tabular value, it is clear that the difference is statistically significant according to the theory of social cognition, which was formulated by Albert Bandura, which indicated that individuals acquire knowledge by observing others and receiving rewards and punishments for their actions. Therefore, female students of the College of Basic Education are empowered through rewards for their empowering actions.

2. Identifying emotional tact among female students of the College of Basic Education.

The arithmetic mean of the research sample on the emotional tact scale was (96.4300) and a standard deviation of (11.19387), while the hypothetical mean was (75). After applying the T-test For one sample, it was shown that the calculated T-value was (5.876) which is significant at the level of (0.05) and the degree of freedom (299), indicating that the female students of the College of Basic Education have emotional tact, and Table (8) shows this.

Table (8). T-test for the significance of the differences between the average scores of emotional tact and the hypothetical average for the sample

Sample	no	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	hypothetical average	Calculated T value	tabular T value	level of significance (0.05)
Students	300	96.4300	11.19387	75	33.159	1.960	Significant

It is clear from the table above that there are statistically significant differences in favor of the research sample in emotional tact, as the arithmetic mean of the sample is higher than its theoretical mean in the scale for the scale. By comparing the calculated T-value with the tabular value, it becomes clear that the difference is statistically significant and the result of the current research is consistent with what was indicated by the study of Shuaib 2022, which indicated that university students generally enjoy emotional tact, males and females.

3. Identify the nature of the relationship between psychological empowerment and emotional tact.

In order to identify the nature of the relationship between psychological empowerment and emotional tact, the researchers used Pearson's correlation coefficient as a statistical method in the treatment, and it was found that there is a significant correlation between psychological empowerment and emotional tact, and the correlation coefficient reached (0.81).

Recommendations

1. The goal of psychological empowerment for female students is to create a society in which women are not generally granted Female students in particular not only have equal rights and opportunities, but they also have the psychological resources they need to deal with and overcome the challenges they face.
2. Focus on the importance of education, enhancing self-confidence, promoting supportive environments, and addressing gender-based violence, which are important in achieving psychological empowerment for women in general and female students in particular.
3. Using psychological empowerment strategies collectively enables women in general and female students in particular to reach their maximum potential, in addition to contributing to developing women's self-efficacy, which is one of the main components of women's psychological empowerment.

Suggestions

In light of the research results, the researchers propose the following:

1. Conduct a study on the psychological empowerment of parental caregivers and its relationship to some variables such as low self-esteem, social withdrawal, and aggression.
2. Conducting a study on the impact of psychological empowerment on the academic achievement of university students.
3. Conducting a comparative study on emotional tact in different communities in the city of Baghdad or other Iraqi cities.

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